

EXPLAINING ARTICLE-POSSESSOR COMPLEMENTARITY: ECONOMIC MOTIVATION IN NOUN PHRASE SYNTAX

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In many languages the definite article cannot occur when a possessive phrase is present in the NP (e.g. English **the my book*, **John's the book*). I argue that these patterns can be understood in terms of economic motivation because possessed NPs are very likely to be definite. A structural explanation in terms of a unique determiner position is insufficient to account for the full range of attested crosslinguistic patterns, and the universal generalizations that do seem to be valid can be derived from the economy-based explanation. Finally I show how the performance motivation of economy creates the competence pattern in diachronic change.*

1. COMPLEMENTARITY. In many languages that normally mark definite noun phrases by a definite article, this article does not occur when a possessive expression is present. This well-known phenomenon is illustrated in 1–2.

(1) English

my book	*the my book	*my the book
Paul's book	*the Paul's book,	*Paul's the book

(2) Spanish

mi libro	*el mi libro	*mi el libro
my book	the my book	my the book

In this article I argue that such patterns of article-possessor complementarity are ECONOMICALLY MOTIVATED (in the sense of Haiman 1983): the definite article can be omitted because possessed NPs have a very high chance of being definite, for semantic and pragmatic reasons that I will explicate. By conventionalizing an articleless possessive construction languages obtain a syntactic pattern that allows for more economical (i.e. shorter) utterances.

This claim may seem surprising for the following three reasons:

(i) One might think that article-possessor complementarity is sufficiently accounted for by noting that the possessive expression and the definite article occur in the same structural position (often called DETERMINER), which cannot be filled twice. Since one fact does not need two explanations, this appears to cast doubt on the economic-motivation account.

(ii) The definite article is by no means entirely redundant in cases like 1 and 2: possessed NPs may perfectly well be indefinite, e.g. *a book of mine*, *a book of Paul's*, Spanish *un libro mío* 'a book of mine'. An economic-motivation account is straightforward in the case of demonstratives, which always make an NP definite. A noun phrase like **a this book* is semantically deviant, so the definite article in **the this book* is truly superfluous. The same does not hold for the article in possessed NPs.

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(iii) Many languages with definite articles do not show any signs of article-possessor complementarity: they have the definite article in all definite NPs, including possessed NPs. A few examples are given in 3–6.¹

(3) Italian

la casa di Davide	la mia casa
ART house of Davide	ART my house
'Davide's house'	'my house'

(4) Modern Greek

to spíti tu patéra	to spíti mu
ART house the father.GEN	ART house I.GEN
'the father's house'	'my house'

(5) Basque

amaren diru-a	zuen liburu-ak
mother.GEN money-ART	you.GEN book-PL.ART
'mother's money'	'your books'

(6) Samoan (Mosel & Hovdhaugen 1992:275)

'o le fale o le ali'i	'o l-o-na fale
PT ART house POSS ART chief	PT ART-POSS-3SG house
'the chief's house'	'his/her house'

The difference between languages like English and languages like Italian has been attributed to a possessive parameter (Lyons 1986:139–40, Giorgi & Longobardi 1991: 155): A (pronominal) possessor may have either determiner status (as in the 'determiner-genitive' language English) or adjective status (as in the 'adjectival-genitive' language Italian). But the economy-based account cannot be so easily parameterized, because economy is a universal functional factor. One expects economy effects to be universally present.

I will address these potential problems for my account in the next three sections, and conclude the discussion by tracing the diachronic development of article-possessor complementarity. It turns out that this pattern arises only in one way during the process of grammaticalization of a definite article from a demonstrative. I claim that article-possessor complementarity cannot arise when the language already has a firmly established definite article. This sheds further light on the way in which languages may come to have economical patterns.

2. THE LACK OF FORMAL CONSTRAINTS ON ARTICLE-POSSESSOR COMPLEMENTARITY. If one looks at West Germanic and Romance languages, a formal constraint on article-possessor complementarity seems to emerge from the data (Table 1):² the definite article is omitted only when the possessor is preposed, that is, if it is potentially in the same

¹ Abbreviations used in interlinear glosses:

ART = definite article	GENART = genitive article	POSS = possessive marker
DAT = dative	INDEFART = indefinite article	PT = particle
GEN = genitive case	PL = plural	SG = singular

² My sources for data from little-known languages presented in Tables 1–4 and 8–10 are as follows: **Abkhaz**, Hewitt 1979:116; **Albanian**, Buchholz & Fiedler 1987:289; **Amharic**, Leslau 1995:50, 155, 193; **Afrikaans**, Donaldson 1993:98; **Aramaic**, Marti 1896; **Breton**, Stephens 1993:141; **Coptic**, Lambdin 1983: 132; **Erzya Mordvin** (Finno-Ugrian), Zavodova & Koljadenkov 1964; **Icelandic**, Sigurðsson 1993:188; **Maltese**, Plank & Moravcsik 1996; **Nkore-Kiga** (Niger-Congo: Bantu), Taylor 1972, 1985:53, 89; **Romanian**, Grosu 1994; **Romani**, Gjerdmán & Ljungberg 1963; **Somali**, Berchem 1991:141; **Sranan**, Bruyn 1998; **Vai** (Niger-Congo: Northern Mande), Welmrs 1976:30, 44; **Welsh**, King 1993:38; **Yiddish**, Katz 1987.

	POSSESSIVE PRONOUN	PREPOSED POSSESSOR	POSTPOSED POSSESSOR
English	my (*the) house	Paul's (*the) house	the roof of the house
German	mein (*das) Haus 'my house'	Pauls (*das) Haus 'Paul's house'	das Haus Pauls/von Paul 'Paul's house'
Dutch	mijn (*het) huis 'my house'	Diks (*het) huis 'Dik's house'	het huis van Dik 'Dik's house'
Afrikaans	my (*die) huis 'my house'	Amanda se (*die) huis 'Amanda's house'	
Yiddish	mayn (*di) shvester 'my sister'	dem yidns (*dos) hoyz 'the Jew's house'	der kharakter fun shtot 'the character of the city'
French	ma (*la) maison 'my house'	—	la maison de Paulette 'Paulette's house'
Spanish	mi (*la) casa 'my house'	—	la casa de Irene 'Irene's house'

TABLE 1. Article-possessor complementarity in Germanic and Romance.

structural position as the definite article. When the possessor is postposed, the article reappears. This is just what one would expect if article-possessor complementarity is attributed to a prenominal determiner position that can only be filled once.

It would seem, therefore, that it is not necessary to invoke economic motivation for these data. But article-possessor complementarity is not restricted to cases in which the article and the possessor would be in the same position. It is also found in languages in which the definite article and the possessor occur on opposite sides of the head noun. In Swedish, Vai, and Amharic, the article is postposed and the possessor is preposed, and the reverse is found in the Semitic and in the Celtic languages (Table 2).

Swedish	bok-en	'the book'	Karins bok(*-en)	'Karin's book'
Vai	bã-ă	'the goat'	kâr-ĕ fã(*-ă)	'the man's father'
Amharic	lăġ-u	'the son'	yă-găbäre-w lăġ(*-u)	'the farmer's son'
Hebrew	ha-sefer	'the book'	(*ha-)sefer David	'David's book'
Maltese	id-dar	'the house'	(*id-)dar Manwel	'Manwel's house'
Welsh	y car	'the car'	(*y) car y meddyg	'the doctor's car'
Irish	an tigh	'the house'	(*an) tigh an tsagairt	'the priest's house'

TABLE 2. Complementarity with different position of article and possessor.

There is further evidence that article-possessor complementarity is not constrained by structural factors. We also find cases in which the article and the possessor are affixes, but they are in complementary distribution in the same way as the syntactic elements of earlier examples (Table 3). Perhaps even more surprising are cases in which the article is an affix, while the possessor is a free expression, and still we find complementary distribution. Examples of this situation are given in Table 4.

Abkhaz (NW Caucasian)	a-y ^o n	'the house'	yə-y ^o nə	'his house'
	ART-house		3SG.POSS-house	
Erzya Mordvin (Finno-Ugrian)	kudo-ś	'the house'	kudo-m	'my house'
	house-ART		house-1SG.POSS	
Amharic (South Semitic)	bet-u	'the house'	bet-e	'my house'
	house-ART		house-1SG.POSS	
Biblical Aramaic (NW Semitic)	malk-ā	'the king'	malk-ī	'my king'
	king-ART		king-1SG.POSS	

TABLE 3. Article-possessor complementarity with affixed article and possessor.

Bulgarian	sestra-ta sister-ART 'the sister'	sestra(*-ta) mi sister(-ART) my 'my sister'
Icelandic	fyrirlestur-inn lecture-ART 'the lecture'	fyrirlestur(*-inn) málfræðings-ins lecture(-ART) linguist.GEN-ART 'the linguist's lecture'
Biblical Aramaic	ʔelāh-ā God-ART '(the) God'	ʔelāh(*-ā) šəmajj-ā God(-ART) Heaven-ART 'the God of (the) Heaven'

TABLE 4. Article-possessor complementarity with affixed article and free possessor.

Thus, across languages we find a wide variety of different construction types with article-possessor complementarity, and no formal constraints on this phenomenon are apparent. This is an argument in favor of my economy-based account, because functional explanations are not expected to be limited by formal constraints. Invariably in each case in Tables 1–4, the article is omitted only when the possessor is present, that is when it is to some extent redundant, and in each case the omission of the article allows more economical utterances. Overall, it seems that the economic-motivation account makes just the right predictions and is not at all made superfluous by the determiner-position analysis.

The determiner-position analysis has won widespread acceptance among syntacticians in recent decades, apparently following Bloomfield's (1933:203) original proposal (see, e.g. Fries 1952:89, Lyons 1986:138, Giorgi & Longobardi 1991, Givón 1995:179). In fact, this analysis has become so standard that it is rarely discussed in the theoretical literature, but it is mentioned in many textbooks and reference grammars (for English: Quirk et al. 1985:326, Givón 1993:255, McCawley 1998:400; for French: Grevisse 1986:§557, Jones 1996:212; for German: Heidolph et al. 1981:306, Eisenberg 1989:160). It is not my purpose here to argue for or against a particular formal description, but I would like to point out that the case for the determiner-position analysis is weakened by the crosslinguistic data cited in this section. If economy is responsible for articleless possessed NPs in languages like Swedish and Hebrew (where no determiner position can be invoked, Table 2), then the determiner position may be unnecessary in languages like English or Spanish as well, at least in accounting for article-possessor complementarity. This suspicion is strengthened by languages in which article-possessor complementarity is optional, like Brazilian Portuguese (cf. also Icelandic in Table 9). This language allows both the Spanish-like pattern lacking the article and the Italian-like pattern with the article.

(7) Brazilian Portuguese (Thomas 1969)

- a. os amigos
the friends
'the friends'
- b. (os) meus amigos
the my friends
'my friends'

A determiner-position analysis of these patterns would have to say that the possessive *meu* is a determiner in *meu amigo*, but an adjective in *o meu amigo*. Here it is clearly more elegant to say that in the construction with possessive pronouns, the definite article is simply optional, but again the pattern can be understood as economically motivated.

Whether or not one would want to maintain the Bloomfieldian determiner-position

analysis,³ it is clear that such an analysis does not make the economy-based account superfluous, so the first problem raised in §1 is not a valid counterargument to my proposal.

3. THE PREFERENCE FOR DEFINITENESS IN POSSESSED NPS. As I noted in §1, possessed noun phrases are not necessarily definite, they are only highly likely to be definite. But a high likelihood of (or preference for) definiteness is sufficient for economic motivation—we find similar cases in many other parts of the grammar. Comrie (1989: 128), for example, argues that we commonly find special case-marking on animate and/or definite patient NPs because normally the patient is less animate and/or definite than the agent, i.e. the more usual situation shows zero-marking for reasons of economy. Similarly, possession of alienable nouns is often overtly coded, contrasting with zero-coded possession of inalienable nouns (Haiman 1983:§1.1.4) because inalienable nouns occur as possessed items much more often than alienable nouns. In these two cases (and many others, e.g. Croft 1990:§7.2), frequency differences are sufficient to motivate the economical coding.

The high frequency of definite possessed NPs means that hearers can predict that a possessed NP will probably be definite, and therefore possessed NPs with the definite article show a redundancy that is exploited by some languages. In this section I will substantiate the claim that possessed NPs have a preference for definiteness, both from the point of view of the theory of definiteness and on the basis of frequency data from text counts.

My discussion of definiteness will be based mainly on Hawkins's (1978, 1991) theory of the semantics and pragmatics of definite and indefinite articles. Hawkins shows that there are two necessary conditions for the use of the definite article, which are sufficient when they are both present: a noun phrase is definite (i) if its referent is locatable in a pragmatic set of entities shared by the speaker and the hearer, that is if it is pragmatically anchored, and (ii) if the referent is unique (or, more precisely, inclusive) within this set. There are various types of pragmatic anchoring, of establishing a set of entities shared by the speaker and the hearer. The best-known type is anaphoric anchoring (8a), but there are other types such as the associative-anaphoric use (8b), the immediate-situation use (8c), and the larger-situation use (8d).

- (8) a. Lucia bought a new cat. Carlo finds **the** cat too big.
- b. I just read a book about Antarctica. **The** author is a Chilean.
- c. Could you open **the** window, please?
- d. **The** bishop will soon start a campaign against child labor.

Most importantly in the present context, a shared pragmatic set may also be established by NP-internal modifiers such as restrictive relative clauses (9a), complement clauses (9b), adnominal adverbials (9c) and possessive phrases (9d). This is the main reason why theories of definiteness that are based on notions like previous mention or familiarity are insufficient. As Fraurud (1990) shows, anaphoric uses of the definite article make up only a small minority of its occurrences in discourse.

³ Over the last decade, syntacticians working in the Chomskyan framework have largely abandoned the determiner-position analysis for independent reasons: possessive expressions are maximal projections and hence cannot occupy a head position such as the D (determiner) position. Thus, article-possessor complementarity is now expressed by a simple language-specific stipulation (see Abney 1987:271 for English, Olsen 1989 and Grosu 1994 for German, Ernst 1992:431 for Irish, Ritter 1991:40 and Siloni 1996:253 for Hebrew). From my perspective, it is interesting that theory-internal considerations, too, cast doubt on the determiner-position analysis, but I argue that there is more to be said here than language-specific stipulations.

- (9) a. Carlo is upset. He finds **the** cat Lucia bought too big.
 b. We were discussing **the** fact that all languages have pronouns.
 c. Please open **the** window above the main entrance.
 d. **The** author of this new book about Antarctica is a Chilean.

Note that not all NP-internal modifiers can establish a shared pragmatic set. For instance, ordinary adjectives do not play this role (thus, out of context an example with the definite article—??*Carlo is upset. He finds the new cat too big*—is impossible, unlike 9a). The reason is that only modifiers containing a referential element may have this function. In the present context it is particularly important that among the adnominal modifiers with an anchoring function are possessive phrases (9d). The first of Hawkins's two conditions for definiteness is thus automatically fulfilled in possessed NPs, so that they are quite likely to be definite (see Koptjevskaja-Tamm 1999 for a similar point). Of course, possessed NPs do not have to be definite: if the second condition, uniqueness, is not fulfilled, we may get an indefinite possessed NP. This is illustrated in 10.

- (10) a. Diana lives in an old house. **The** ⟨*a⟩ roof was damaged in the last thunderstorm, and **a** ⟨*the⟩ window broke.
 b. **A** ⟨*the⟩ window of Diana's house broke, and **the** ⟨*a⟩ roof of the house was damaged.

Since houses have only one roof and (at least in many cultures) more than one window, the definite article must be used with *roof* in 10, and the indefinite article must be used with *window*, although the pragmatic and syntactic context is almost identical. Thus, it is by no means necessary, only relatively likely, for possessed NPs to be definite.

This prediction from the theory of definiteness is borne out by frequency data from texts. Table 5 shows the results of my counts of two English texts, each containing five hundred NPs. Since I see no reason why spoken language should differ significantly from written language in the relevant respect, I chose written texts for convenience.

	ALL NPS	POSSESSED NPS
total NPs	1000	311
definite NPs	673	292
indefinite NPs	327 (33%)	19 (6%)

TABLE 5. Text frequency of definite and indefinite NPs in English.

Sources: David Lodge, *Small world*, Harmondsworth: Penguin, 1984, 3–13; John le Carré, *The Russia House*, Sevenoaks: Hodder and Stoughton, 1989, 19–31.

Of the one thousand referential full NPs,⁴ almost one third are possessed, i.e., they have a preposed possessor or a postposed possessive phrase marked by *of*. The figures in Table 5 show that of the possessed NPs, the overwhelming majority (94%) are definite (I counted articleless NPs like *my book*, *Joan's book* as definite).⁵ By contrast,

⁴ I excluded pronouns from consideration, because they cannot be possessed or have definite articles. In addition, I did not count nonreferential NPs. As noted, these do not have an anchoring function when occurring as NP-internal modifiers, and this correlates with their syntactic behavior: They do not exclude definite articles, cf. possessed NPs with nonreferential ('classifying') genitives like *bird's nest*, *doll's house* (*the bird's nest* is [*the [bird's nest]*], not [*the bird's nest*]) (see Koptjevskaja-Tamm 1999 for extensive discussion of such 'nonanchoring' genitives in Swedish).

⁵ When an NP containing a preposed possessor is in predicative position, it is not necessarily interpreted as being unique: *this guy is my friend*, e.g., does not presuppose that he is the only friend I have. This must have to do with the fact that the reference of the predicative NP is already established by the subject NP, so in some sense a uniqueness interpretation is not necessary for definiteness. But whatever the correct explanation, predicative NPs were excluded from my counts because they are nonreferential (n. 4 above), so my conclusions are not affected.

when all NPs are considered, the proportion of indefinite NPs is much higher. The textual data thus confirm the prediction that possessed NPs are much more likely to be definite than NPs in general. Thus the prediction implicit in Hawkins's theory of definiteness is vindicated by observable data from texts.

One could of course object to these conclusions on the grounds that English displays a structural bias towards definiteness in possessed NPs: indefinite possessed NPs sometimes require a more complex construction, e.g. *a friend of Yuri's* vs. *Yuri's friend*; *a book of mine* vs. *my book*. Hence the difference in frequencies could be a result of a markedness disparity between the two types of structure. In order to forestall this objection, I also made text counts for Italian and Modern Greek, two languages in which the presence of a possessor has no effect on the article of the possessed NP (see 3 and 4 above),⁶ and in which indefinite possessed NPs have the same structure as definite ones. The results of these counts are shown in Tables 6 and 7.

	ALL NPS	POSSESSED NPS
total NPs	1000	173
definite NPs	745	163
indefinite NPs	255 (26%)	10 (6%)

TABLE 6. Text frequency of definite and indefinite NPs in Italian.

Sources: Mario Tobino, *Il perduto amore*, Milan: Mondadori, 1979, 25–40; Susanna Tamaro, *Anima mundi*, Milan: Baldini & Castoldi, 1997, 69–82.

	ALL NPS	POSSESSED NPS
total NPs	1000	304
definite NPs	757	292
indefinite NPs	243 (24%)	12 (4%)

TABLE 7. Text frequency of definite and indefinite NPs in Modern Greek.

Sources: Níkos Kazandzákis, *O ftoxúlis tu Theú*, Athens: El. Kazandzákis, 1973, 11–22; Kóstas Dzamális, *Stin Athína tu Periklí*, Athens: I. Kollaru, n.d., 22–37.

Since different texts were counted for the three languages, we would not expect the frequency figures to coincide perfectly, but all three languages pattern alike in that possessed NPs are substantially more likely to be definite than NPs in general. I argue that this makes it worthwhile for speakers to create grammars that save them production energy by omitting the definite article in possessed NPs. But of course, speakers cannot consciously manipulate their competence systems so as to allow them to produce efficient utterances. Thus, they 'create' grammars only in a metaphorical sense. How such energy-saving grammars arise as an unintended side effect of speakers' behavior is an important question that I will address in §5.

4. IMPLICATIONAL UNIVERSALS. The third problem identified in §1 is that of crosslinguistic variation: why do some languages (e.g. Italian, ex. 3) not exhibit article-possessor complementarity although the motivating factor of economy is universally present? The answer is straightforward: performance economy is not the only motivating factor that can be conventionalized in grammatical structure. Utterances should not only be economical, but also explicit (in this case, definite NPs should be marked as such).

⁶ In Italian, the article is dropped with possessive pronouns in a small class of nouns, kinship terms (Table 9 below). These were excluded from consideration in my count.

These two factors are often in conflict with each other (see Haiman 1983), and languages like Italian resolve the conflict in favor of explicitness in their conventionalized rules. In optimality-theoretic parlance, one would say that both economy and explicitness are violable constraints, and that languages like English have ranked economy over explicitness, while the reverse ranking is found in languages like Italian.

This competing-motivation account is not vacuous because it does not allow all logically possible language types. As with other competing-motivation analyses (Croft 1990:§7.4), it makes a prediction that can be stated in the familiar form of an implicational universal.⁷

- (11) **Universal 1:** If possessed NPs show the definite article, then so do nonpossessed NPs.

This universal allows economical inexplicit languages (e.g. English), explicit uneconomical languages (e.g. Italian), and languages that completely lack definite articles (e.g. Russian), but it excludes uneconomical inexplicit languages: languages that (uneconomically) have the definite article in possessed NPs but (inexplicitly) lack the definite article in nonpossessed NPs.

Furthermore, the perspective of utterance economy also allows us to make two somewhat more subtle universal predictions. Languages show an increased tendency to omit the definite article when the possessor is preposed (rather than postposed) and when the possessed noun is a kinship term. This allows us to formulate two additional implicational universals.

Table 1 shows that in the West Germanic and Romance languages, the preposed possessors, but not the postposed possessors, are in complementary distribution with the definite article. At first glance, this restriction looks like a logical consequence of the fact that the definite article is preposed in these languages. Additional data however, show that the correct generalization is different: preposed possessors are more likely to cause article omission than postposed ones independently of the position of the article. Some data in support of this claim are shown in Table 8.

	PREPOSED POSSESSOR DEFINITE ARTICLE OMITTED	POSTPOSED POSSESSOR DEFINITE ARTICLE PRESENT
English	our dog's (*the) kennel	the kennel of our dog
Spanish	(*el) mi libro (the) my book	el libro mío the book my
Yiddish	(*di) mayn shvester (the) my sister	di shvester di mayne the sister the my
Romani	(*le) murré raklés (the) my boy	le raklés le murrés the boy the my
Swedish	min vän(*-nen) my friend(-ART)	vänn-en min friend-ART my
Icelandic	mitt hús(*-ið) my house(-ART)	hús(-ið) mitt house(-ART) my
Romanian	ai nostri tineri(*-i) GENART our youngsters(-ART)	tineri-i nostri youngsters-ART our
Albanian	im vëlla(*-i) my brother(-ART)	vëlla-i im brother-ART my

TABLE 8. Increased omissibility with preposed possessors.

⁷ This universal is quite parallel to the textbook example involving number marking (Croft 1990:68): 'If the singular is expressed by a nonzero morpheme, then so is the plural.'

In Yiddish and Romani, the possessive pronoun is in complementary distribution with the article when it precedes the noun, but cooccurs with the article (actually, two instances of the article) when it follows the noun. Even more striking are the data from Swedish, Icelandic, Romanian and Albanian. In these languages, the definite article regularly follows the noun; the possessor is only compatible with it when it follows the noun as well. Clearly, then, it is the position of the possessor with respect to the head noun, not with respect to the article, that is crucial. I hypothesize that the pattern in Table 8 reflects a general tendency which can be formulated as an implicational universal.

- (12) **Universal 2:** If possessed NPs with a preposed possessor show the definite article, then so do possessed NPs with a postposed possessor.

The fact that articles are more likely to be omitted with preposed possessors finds a natural explanation within my economy-based approach: if the possessor precedes the head noun, then at the time the hearer encounters the head noun he or she already has the information about its probable definiteness.⁸ Thus, overt indication of definiteness is still more redundant under these circumstances. Conversely, the definite article is relatively more useful with postposed possessors because at the time the head noun is encountered the anchoring information of the possessor is not yet available. My proposal thus is that Universal 2 reflects the conventionalization of precedence preferences during on-line processing—there is no implication that anchoring indicators should occur in a particular structural position.⁹ Linear precedence in processing has been shown to play an important role in other areas of grammar as well, for instance Jespersen's (1917: 5) NEGATIVE FIRST PRINCIPLE (cf. Horn 1989: ch. 7 for new evidence for this principle), as well as Hawkins's (1994) principle of EARLY IMMEDIATE CONSTITUENTS.

The tendency to omit the definite article is also greater when the possessed noun is a kinship term. One might attribute this to the fact that kinship nouns are often treated as proper names and may therefore dispense with the definite article. But in the languages in Table 9, the article is omitted only when the noun is possessed, so the presence of the possessor is crucial. The pattern of Table 9 can be summarized by an implicational universal.

- (13) **Universal 3:** If possessed NPs with a kinship term as head noun show the definite article, then so do possessed NPs with a nonkinship term as head noun.

I propose that articles are more likely to be omitted with kinship nouns because the possessive relation is inherent in them: kinship terms, like other inalienable nouns, are semantically relational, that is they are conceptually incomplete when they are not possessed. As Barker (1992) has pointed out, the pragmatic anchoring is particularly effective in the case of inalienable possession. Thus, the minidiscourse 14 is quite normal, whereas 15, with a nonrelational (or alienable) noun, is infelicitous.

⁸ I am assuming that all syntactic, semantic, and pragmatic information that can be associated with an item on-line is made immediately available, as has been argued by Marslen-Wilson & Tyler 1980 and Hawkins 1994, for example.

⁹ Further confirming evidence comes from the fact that there is an analogous asymmetry in the patterns of article-demonstrative complementarity. There are several languages in which only preposed demonstratives, but not postposed demonstratives, are incompatible with the definite article, e.g. Romanian *acest om* 'this man' vs. *om-ul acest* 'man-the this'; Spanish *este libro* 'this book' vs. *el libro este* 'the book this'; Sranan *disi buku* 'this book' vs. *a buku disi* 'the book this'; Hebrew *ze sefer* 'this book' vs. *ha-sefer ha-ze* 'the-book the-this'; Nkore-Kiga *eki kitabo* 'this book' vs. *e-kitabo eki* 'ART-book this'. Again, the asymmetry is independent of formal considerations such as the position of the article, so only the economy-based explanation makes the correct prediction.

	KINSHIP NOUN	OTHER HEAD NOUN
Italian	(* <i>la</i>) <i>mia madre</i>	<i>la mia casa</i>
	(the) my mother	the my house
Brazilian Portuguese	(* <i>a</i>) <i>minha mãe</i>	(<i>a</i>) <i>minha casa</i>
	(the) my mother	(the) my house
Bulgarian	<i>majka</i> (* <i>-ta</i>) <i>mi</i>	<i>kola-ta mi</i>
	mother(-ART) my	car-ART my
Icelandic	<i>sonur</i> (* <i>-inn</i>) <i>minn</i>	<i>hús</i> (<i>i-ð</i>) <i>mitt</i>
	son(-ART) my	house(-ART) my
Somali	<i>hooya-day</i> (* <i>-du</i>)	<i>saxiib-kay-gu</i>
	mother-1SG.POSS(-ART)	friend-1SG.POSS-ART
Nkore-Kiga	'my mother'	'my friend'
	(* <i>o-</i>) <i>mukuru wangye</i>	<i>e-kitabo kyangye</i>
	(ART) <i>sister my</i>	ART-book my
Vai	'my sister'	'my book'
	<i>kàí-ě fǎ</i> (* <i>-ǎ</i>)	<i>kàí-ě á kég-ě</i>
	man-ART father(-ART)	man-ART POSS house-ART
	'the man's father'	'the man's house'

TABLE 9. Increased omissibility with kinship nouns.

(14) A man came in. His daughter was with him.

(15) A man came in. #His monkey was with him.

In the case of nonrelational nouns, the hearer must search for a suitable pragmatic link in the context to license the possessive relation and the definite interpretation. This link is automatically given in relational nouns. The definite article is therefore relatively more redundant in kinship terms, and relatively more useful in nonrelational nouns, a difference that is exploited in the grammars of some languages.¹⁰

Thus, none of the three problems mentioned in §1 is a sufficient counterargument to my explanation in terms of economic motivation. Since this analysis is fairly simple and straightforward, it is surprising that it has been so rarely proposed previously—I have come across an explicit formulation of this explanation only twice in previous theoretical work (Serebrennikov 1968:75, Koptjevskaja-Tamm 1999).

5. THE DIACHRONIC ORIGIN OF ARTICLE-POSSESSOR COMPLEMENTARITY. In order to understand how economic motivation functions in language, it is instructive to examine the diachronic development of article-possessor complementarity. As Bybee (1988) has noted, diachronic considerations are essential if we want to give a complete explanation of the facts, because it is in language change that performance influences competence.

Logically, there are two main ways in which a complementary distribution of articles and possessors may have come about. In the first scenario, a language may at one time have had no complementarity, i.e. the schematic pattern [ART-N] for nonpossessed definite NPs and the pattern [ART-POSS-N] for possessed definite NPs. Then a change occurred by which the article was eliminated in possessed NPs (for reasons of economy), leading to the new patterns [ART-N]/[POSS-N]. We can call this the *ELIMINATION SCENARIO*. In the second scenario, a language may at one time have had no definite article, so it had the pattern [N] for nonpossessed definite NPs and the pattern [POSS-N] for possessed definite NPs. Then a change occurred by which a definite article was intro-

¹⁰ In addition to kinship terms, there are other relational nouns, e.g. body part terms. I do not know why these behave differently in most of the languages mentioned. But there is at least one language, Vai (Welmers 1976:44), where body part terms pattern with kinship terms.

duced into the language. The definite article did not become established in possessed NPs, however, because definiteness marking is to some extent redundant in this environment. Again, the resulting new patterns are [ART-N]/[POSS-N]. We can call this the INHIBITION SCENARIO.

The available evidence strongly suggests that the inhibition scenario is responsible for complementary patterns in languages, and that the elimination scenario is not just unattested, but impossible. Let us begin by looking at the inhibition scenario in more detail. As is well known, definite articles usually arise through the grammaticalization of demonstrative pronouns (see, e.g., Greenberg 1978), and during the initial stages of this process the new article is used often but is not yet obligatory. Over time, the loose construction allowing a high degree of variation and optionality is gradually transformed into a fixed construction with increasingly obligatory elements and rules. This common diachronic process is often called SYNTACTICIZATION.¹¹

In all the languages with article-possessor complementarity that have a sufficiently long written tradition, we see that the definite article has arisen fairly recently, and a stage of a looser, variable construction is sometimes still attested. In the Germanic languages, for instance, the stage of an optional definite article can be observed in Gothic (cf. Sauvageot 1929). Thus in 16, taken from the Gothic Bible, the first NP has an article, but the second NP lacks it, without any apparent grammatical conditioning (the Greek original has the definite article in both NPs).

- (16) ik im þata weinatriu, iþ jus weinainos (John 15.5)
 I am the vine but ye branches
 'I am the vine, ye are the branches.'

The same variability can also be observed when a possessor is present, as is shown in 17a–d (with the additional factor of the relative word-order freedom of the possessive).

- | | | | |
|---------|----------------------------|----|--------------------------------|
| (17) a. | mein bloþ (John 6.54) | b. | so meina laiseins (John 7.16) |
| | my blood | | the my doctrine |
| | 'my blood' | | 'my doctrine' |
| c. | saiwala meina (John 10.15) | d. | sa þiumagus meins (Matth. 8.8) |
| | soul my | | the servant my |
| | 'my soul' | | 'my servant' |

In the West Germanic and Nordic languages, a similar development has taken place over the last millennium (cf. Hodler 1954). The optional use of the definite article in possessive constructions gradually gave way to its total elimination in that environment via the syntacticization of the more frequent alternatives (though some contemporary Nordic languages still show word order variability and optionality—Swedish and Icelandic in Table 8).

The history of Romance articles is quite similar. Old Italian (Old Tuscan; exx. 18a–d, from Rohlfs 1968:127) shows a degree of variation analogous to that in Gothic. Rohlfs observes that the definite article with possessives became general at a relatively late date.

¹¹ Sometimes also GRAMMATICALIZATION, as in Hawkins's (1994) performance theory of word order and constituency. Hawkins's approach is very similar to mine in that he argues that the patterns of the competence grammar can be explained by properties of performance. (The term GRAMMATICALIZATION is more often used for the general diachronic scenario by which loose concatenations of free words turn into tight combinations of words with their affixes (see e.g. Lehmann 1995). I use the term in this more general sense, of which syntacticization is a special case.)

- | | | | |
|---------|---|----|--|
| (18) a. | miei giorni
my days
'my days' | b. | lo tuo padre
the your father
'your father' |
| c. | la loro potenza
the their power
'their power' | d. | lo viso mio
the face my
'my face' |

As the article constructions became more fixed through syntacticization, the patterns showing the greatest performance economy were selected in many Germanic and Romance languages, and the noneconomical patterns were inhibited and gradually died out.

Now let us examine the first scenario sketched above, the elimination scenario. A priori, this scenario looks simpler than the inhibition scenario, and one might expect to find it attested as well. However, this possibility can be virtually excluded because speakers cannot normally drop morphological material in highly grammaticalized constructions. In order to economize, speakers reduce their utterances phonetically, not morphosyntactically (see Lüdtke 1980, 1985 for general discussion of this point). Thus, I expect all patterns of article-possessor complementarity to have arisen in the process of the grammaticalization of the definite article.

If this is true, it follows that all languages with article-possessor complementarity must have a relatively young definite article. Relatively young here means younger than the possessive construction. This is certainly true in the case of the Germanic and Romance preposed possessor, which continues a possessive construction that is at least two millennia old, whereas the definite article arose just little more than a thousand years ago. If, however, the definite article is older than the possessive construction, it is predicted that the resulting pattern will not exhibit article-possessor complementarity. This is strikingly confirmed by evidence from languages with an established definite article in which a new possessive construction is created by grammaticalization. There are quite a few languages in which such a new possessive construction exists side by side with the old one (generally with differences in usage which are irrelevant here). A selection of these is given in Table 10.

	OLD POSSESSIVE CONSTRUCTION	>	NEW POSSESSIVE CONSTRUCTION
English	the planet's destruction	>	the destruction of the planet
German	meines Bruders Haus my brother's house	>	das Haus von meinem Bruder the house of my brother
Norwegian	engelskman-en-s båt Englishman-ART-GEN boat	>	båt-en til engelskman-en boat-ART of Englishman-ART
Irish	mo leabhar my book	>	an leabhar agam the book to.me
Breton	kelennerien ar Skol Veur lecturers the university	>	ar c'helennerien eus ar Skol Veur the lecturers from the university
Hebrew	sefer ha-talmid book the-pupil	>	ha-sefer šel ha-talmid the-book of the-pupil
Maltese	dar it-tifel house the-boy	>	id-dar ta-t-tifel the-house of-the-boy
Hungarian	a barát könyv-e the brother book-3SG.POSS 'the brother's book'	>	a barát-nak a könyv-e the brother-DAT the book-3SG.POSS 'the brother's book'
Coptic	hēt-əs belly-3SG.F.POSS 'her belly'	>	te-s-hēt ART-3SG.F.POSS-belly 'her belly'

TABLE 10. Old and new possessive constructions.

These languages show considerable formal diversity in their old and new possessive constructions (case marking, prepositional marking, or head marking), but they are uniform with respect to the behavior of definite articles: in all nine languages the definite article is omitted from the head noun in the old possessive construction, but it is not omitted in the newly grammaticalized possessive construction. One can thus predict quite generally that whenever a language shows article-possessor complementarity in a possessive construction, this possessive construction was syntacticized not later than the definite article in the language. As far as I can tell, this is consistent with what is known about the history of the languages mentioned in this paper.

Thus, article-possessor complementarity seems to be due primarily to the inhibition scenario: at an early stage of the syntacticization of the definite article, speakers use the articleless construction more often for reasons of economy, so the definite article cannot spread to these environments and the articleless construction becomes fixed (unless, of course, the competing motivation of explicitness is valued more highly). Thus, an economical pattern in the competence grammar is created, although there is no conscious intention to create anything (see Keller 1994 for this paradox of language change).

6. CONCLUSION. I have argued in this article that the omission of the definite article in definite possessed NPs should be attributed to economic motivation. Possessed NPs have a very high chance of being definite for semantic and pragmatic reasons (§3), and the resulting redundancy is exploited by some languages in which possessed NPs lack a definite article. The speakers' preference for economical utterances becomes part of the grammatical conventions through diachronic change: article-possessor complementarity arises diachronically when a new definite article is grammaticalized in a language but does not spread all the way to possessed NPs (§5). Not all languages exhibit article-possessor complementarity because of the competing motivation of explicitness (§4).

This account raises questions about a number of related phenomena which, though they fall outside the scope of the present investigation, should at least be mentioned here. Note that there are other nominal modifiers, in particular demonstratives and superlatives, that make a definite interpretation very likely or even necessary. Interestingly, these exhibit the same kind of crosslinguistic variation seen in article-possessor complementarity. Some languages require the definite article in these contexts (e.g. Hungarian *ez a ház* lit. 'this the house', English *the biggest boy*), while others show complementary distribution of the demonstrative/superlative and the definite article (e.g. English *this (*the) house*, Arabic *ʔakbar (*al-)walad* lit. 'biggest boy'). Furthermore, because of their uniqueness semantics, proper names are almost always definite, and again we find the same pattern of variation (e.g. English *(*the) Mary*, but Modern Greek *i María*, lit. 'the Maria'). It seems natural to extend the economy-based account (including the competing motivation of explicitness) to these cases.

Another question to consider is the cooccurrence possibilities between possessives and other determinerlike elements such as demonstratives (*??this my book*, Plank 1992), distributive quantifiers (*his every word*), and indefinite articles (**a my book*). To the extent that a consistent pattern is found here, a formal analysis in terms of a determiner position may well be the best solution. My arguments against the determiner-position analysis in §2 should not be construed as rejecting this notion completely. The only claim in that section was that a determiner-position account of article-possessor complementarity does not make the economic-motivation account superfluous.

One should be careful though to avoid making strong claims on the basis of just a few similar languages. A comparison of English and French with Italian and Russian suggests the correlation among three features shown in Table 11 (cf. Schoorlemmer 1998:62).

	TYPE 1 (Italian, Russian)		TYPE 2 (English, French)
(a) determiner is compatible with possessor	+		-
(b) possessed NP may be indefinite	+		-
(c) possessive pronoun may be used independently	+		-
	Italian	English	French
(a) il/questo mio libro	èta moja kniga	(*the/??this) my book	(*le/ce) mon livre
(b) un mio libro	odna moja kniga	*a my book	*un mon livre
(c) questo libro è mio	èta kniga—moja	*this book is my	*ce livre est mon

TABLE 11. Schoorlemmer's (1998) Type 1 and Type 2 languages.

This correlation seems to support the analysis of pronominal possessives as adjectives in Italian and Russian, but as determiners in English and French (Lyons 1986, Giorgi & Longobardi 1991). The third feature, independent occurrence in predicative position, would fall out automatically from such a categorization, but data from additional languages cast serious doubts on the validity of the correlation in Table 11. As Giorgi & Longobardi (1991:159–60) note themselves, many northern Italian varieties have different pronominal possessives in adnominal and predicative positions, e.g. Paduan *el me libro* 'my book', but *sto libro ze mio* 'this book is mine'. These data undermine the claim that it is the adjectival status of *mio* in Italian that is responsible for the English/French-Italian contrasts. In addition, there are languages that resemble Italian in that the definite article cooccurs with the possessive, but resemble English and French in that the indefinite article cannot cooccur with the possessive (e.g. Romanian *profesorul meu* 'my teacher', but **un profesor meu* 'a teacher of mine', Grosu 1994). Finally, in some languages the article/demonstrative is incompatible with a possessor, but possessed NPs may be indefinite (e.g. Singlish (= Colloquial Singaporean English) **the/that Jamil apple* 'Jamil's apple', but *Jamil apple* 'an apple of Jamil's', Gil 1999). So in addition to the feature combinations $+/+/+$ and $-/-/-$ of Table 11, we also find $+/+/-$ (Paduan), $+/-/+$ (Romanian), $-/+/-$ (Singlish). Thus, without a fuller picture of the possibilities across languages, it seems premature to draw conclusions about the determiner status of the possessive phrase.

While studying article-possessor complementarity in a wide range of languages, I have found no purely formal constraints on the conditions under which article-possessor complementarity may occur (§2). Those generalizations that do seem to be valid universally, formulated as implicational universals in §4, can be related directly to economic motivation.

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